

Rare cause of cerebral damage: child with heatstroke found inside an enclosed vehicle

造成腦創傷的罕見原因：兒童在密閉車輛內中暑

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Many children suffer from preventable diseases. Heat stress is one of the neglected causes of mortality and morbidity. We report here the clinical features of a 3-year-old boy who suffered from near-fatal heatstroke in an enclosed car. He developed multiple organs failure, including neurological insult, acute renal failure, and disseminated intravascular coagulation. Although life-threatening complications were treated with supportive measures and conventional external cooling in the intensive care unit, neurological sequelae persisted. This type of heatstroke is almost always preventable. Similar to many other pediatric emergencies, it can be life-threatening and may result in severe untoward outcomes. (Hong Kong j.emerg.med. 2012;19:126-129)

許多兒童患有可預防的疾病。熱刺激是常被忽略可引致死亡和發病率的原因之一。在這裡，我們報告一位3歲男孩在密閉的汽車中暑幾乎致命的個案。他發生多器官的功能衰竭，包括神經系統和腎功能衰竭、瀰漫性血管內凝血障礙。雖然在加護病房以體外冷卻及支持性治療致命的併發症，但神經系統後遺症依然發生。這類型的中暑是可以預防的。像其他兒科急症，可危及生命，並引致嚴重的不良後果。

Keywords: Automobiles, heat stress disorder, motor vehicle

關鍵詞：汽車、熱刺激、機動車

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Introduction

Heat-related conditions and diseases have been observed at increasing rates since the emerge of global warming. Hyperthermia occurs when the body temperature rises above the hypothalamic set point. Heat-related conditions from mild to severe include heat stress, heat exhaustion, and heatstroke. Heatstroke is a life-threatening condition characterised by a core body temperature of $>40^{\circ}\text{C}$ and is accompanied by mental status changes. Cars are an indispensable part of our daily life, and to own a vehicle is easy in many countries. Hundreds of children experience varying

degrees of heat illness.¹ Infant and early childhood death caused by environmental hyperthermia is rare, and it usually occurs in vehicles or beds.² It has been reported that every year, many children die from heatstroke after being left unattended inside a vehicle.³ This danger still exists despite public education efforts against leaving children unattended in vehicles. In this case report, a child with cerebral damage caused by heatstroke in an enclosed car is presented with relevant literature.

Case

A three year old boy admitted to emergency room for loss of consciousness. Detailed medical history revealed that he was left in a car unattended in an open place for about 5 hours. On physical examination, he was comatose, dehydrated and was not responding to noxious stimuli. The Glasgow Coma Score (GCS) was 3 (E₁V₁M₁). Heart rate was 156/min, respiratory rate was 52/min and blood pressure was 75/40 mmHg. Acidotic respiration was remarkable. Core temperature was measured by rectal thermometer and it was 41°C. He was immediately and intensively cooled by undressing and splashing of tap water (-20°C) on his body. Because of hypotension intravenous crystalloid and dopamine infusion was started. Ten minutes later his core temperature was still 40.5°C, ice packs were placed on neck, axilla and groin. After 30 minute his body temperature decreased to 40°C. Despite external cooling his conscious was still blurry and he was areflexic and being comatose [GCS was 4 (E₁V₁M₂)], endotracheal intubation and mechanical ventilation was started at paediatric intensive care unit. Although routine biochemical and haematologic parameters such as BUN (blood urea nitrogen), creatinine, serum protein, albumin, lactate, sodium, potassium, glucose, AST (aspartate transaminase), ALT (alanine transaminase), ammonium, haemoglobine, haematocrite, white blood cell and thrombocyte counts were within normal ranges, blood coagulation panel demonstrated high prothrombin (35 sec) and activated partial thromboplastin time (56 sec), suggesting disseminated intravascular coagulation. Blood gas analysis demonstrated metabolic acidosis (pH: 7.23, pO₂:

117 mmHg, pCO₂: 41.8, bicarbonate 8.6 mmol/L). Fresh frozen plasma, and intravenous fluid and electrolyte and slow administration of sodium bicarbonate were added to his treatment. Cranial computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance (MR) imaging demonstrated diffuse cerebral oedema, severe gyral thickening and patchy areas of T2 hyperintensity (see Figure 1). The patient started to have seizures the next day of admission. Mannitol and furocemide as well as antiepileptic treatment (phenytoin 10 mg/kg/day) was initiated. Electroencephalography (EEG) showed diffuse base line slowing as well as dysrhythmia. Seizures were not repeated after second day of anti-epileptic and anti-oedema treatment. His GCS was gradually improved and it was 11 (E₄V₃M₄) on the ninth day of admission. Additionally he was not able to speak and his extremities were found spastic. He was discharged after 17 days of admission with quadriparesis, bilaterally weak light reflex and no ability to follow objects. There was visual evoked response abnormality and regression

Figure 1. Coronal T2 weighed brain image showed effacement of fissure and sulci as well as gyral thickening and patchy areas of hyperintensity. Similar findings were present in the cerebellum.

of developmental milestones with loss of ambulation due to spastic tetraplegia. He was not referred again after discharge.

Discussion

Heatstroke is a problem for all ages; infants, children, and elderly people are at particularly great risk. Infants and small children have insufficient body surface and should avoid the harmful effects of excess heat. In addition, they have an inefficient rate of sweating. The heat regulation centre often functions improperly in elderly people.^{4,5} Heatstroke refers to a situation in which individuals exposed to high environmental temperatures experience hyperthermia and neurologic dysfunction, manifested by disorientation, lethargy, delirium, and coma.² It is usually associated with multiorgan dysfunction, such as coagulation abnormalities, electrolyte and fluid imbalances, renal dysfunction, and even rhabdomyolysis. The incidence of heatstroke varies from 17.6 to 26.5/100 000 in the United States and 22 to 250/100 000 in Saudi Arabia. The mortality rate also varies from 10% to 70% depending on the severity of the condition and age of the patient.^{6,7} Heatstroke is often fatal, especially in children, and frequently results in neurological disability.⁸

The major therapeutic interventions in patients with heatstroke are immediate cooling and support of organ system functions.⁹ Prompt measurement of core body temperature is essential, and immediate cooling must be initiated in the field with available external techniques. Alcohol sponges, ice packs, and splashing of cold or icy tap water onto the body can be practiced in the field or emergency room.⁵ Other advanced interventions that must be administered in the emergency room include cold intravenous fluid infusion and gastric lavage with cold water.⁵ More advanced heat-lowering techniques, such as heat exchange balloons, iced peritoneal lavage, cardiopulmonary bypass, and cold continuous haemofiltration, are internal cooling techniques,^{10,11} but most health care centres do not have these facilities. In the present case, we used conventional external

cooling techniques (ice packs to the axilla, neck, and groin and fanning with large fans).

Recovery is poor if patients have central nervous system (CNS) dysfunction, persistent hypotension, and decreased cardiac output at the beginning. The majority of survivors have near normal renal, neurologic, and haematologic functions. Twenty percent of patients will experience residual brain damage, and another 33% will have functional disability at discharge.¹² Our patient was discharged with visual abnormality and regression of developmental milestones in concordance with the literature.

The most challenging complication of heatstroke is multiple organ failure,^{5,13} which includes encephalopathy, acute renal failure, and disseminated intravascular coagulation. Although our patient had all of these life-threatening conditions, he was successfully treated with supportive measures.

Neurological involvement is the most catastrophic sequel, with patients presenting to the hospital in a deep coma and with flaccid paralysis, hyper-reflexia, seizures, and a high incidence of permanent neurological deficits.^{8,14} The described imaging findings in heatstroke include early cerebral oedema, central pontine myelinolysis,¹⁴ vascular boundary zone infarcts and, in later stages, diffuse cerebellar atrophy.¹⁵ Our patient presented in a deep coma and demonstrated coagulation abnormalities. Prompt intervention prevented bleeding complications. Epileptic seizures seen in our patient were the result of severe brain insult, and imaging studies confirmed severe cytotoxic cerebral oedema and subsequent neuron loss and glial proliferation. The prognosis is better when heatstroke is diagnosed early and management with cooling measures and fluid resuscitation and electrolyte replacement begins promptly. If patients have initial CNS dysfunction, persistent hypotension, and decreased cardiac output, the prognosis is poorest.⁵

Young children and infants are more susceptible to heat illness than adults for several reasons. Physiologically, toddlers and infants, despite their increased body surface area to mass ratio, seem to have less effective

thermoregulation, as compared with adults.^{4,5,16} McLaren et al demonstrated that on sunny days, even when the ambient temperature is mild or relatively cool, there is rapid and significant heating of the interior of vehicles.¹⁷ On days when the ambient temperature was 22°C, that study showed that the internal vehicle temperature can reach 47°C within 60 minutes, with 80% of the temperature rise occurring in the first 30 minutes. They also determined that cracking open windows is not effective in decreasing either the rate of heat rise or the maximum temperature attained.¹⁷

Another aspect of these cases involves legal issues. In the United States, leaving a child unattended in a vehicle is illegal. Our case constituted an example of neglect, which is the most common form of child abuse.¹⁸ Prevention of heat illness in children is crucial, and leaving a child unattended in a car not only on hot days but also on cool, sunny days, may subject the child to significant risks of mortality and morbidity due to heatstroke. Prompt and immediate diagnosis and reduction of body temperature is essential to avoid the worst outcomes. Intensive care management and supporting measures can result in patient survival and recovery. Nonetheless, there is little known about the prognosis and appropriate and effective management of patients with heatstroke; more data are needed.

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